
SETTING ASIDE AN ARBITRAL AWARD UNDER SECTION 34, ARBITRATION & CONCILIATION ACT, 2019

BY SATYAM¹

ABSTRACT

Arbitration is a means of resolving disputes quickly and without much litigation. The Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996, along with its amendments in 2015 and 2019, provide under Section 34 the grounds for challenging arbitral awards and the procedure to do so. These grounds include incapacity of the parties, procedural unfairness, contrary to public policy, and awards outside the scope of arbitration. The challenges must be made within an extremely short time of three months, which can be extended by a further 30 days, thus ensuring swiftness. The aim of amendments is to facilitate efficiency and at the same time naturalizes judicial control, while the court should not interfere with awards simply on the grounds of factual or legal errors. Overall, the framework creates a balance between the finality related to the arbitral aspect and the other fair and due process considerations in the resolution of disputes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Arbitration is a method of resolving disputes outside of the courts without going through the lengthy procedures given under the statutes. This approach helps in reducing the burden of the court as well as facilitating a settlement which is mutually amicable to both the parties.

Section 34 of the Arbitration & Conciliation Act, 1996² (“**the Act**”) served as an instrument for filing an application against the arbitral awards passed by any tribunal by a party aggrieved by the award, while Section 34(2)³ of the Act provides the grounds for challenging an arbitral award rendered under Section 31⁴ of this Act by an arbitral tribunal.

However, the limitation period for filing the application under this Section is given under the sub-section (3) of the Act which is 3 months of receiving the award.⁵ There is a provision for extension for which is for another 30 days on the discretion of the tribunal. The award passed

¹ Author is a student of B.A. LL.B. at Vivekananda Institute of Professional Studies, GGSIPU

² S-34, Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

³ S-34(2), Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

⁴ S-31, Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

⁵ S-34(3), Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

by the tribunal is to be treated as the final judgement and the parties should stick and adhere to it. It is a settled rule that the parties constitute the arbitral tribunal as a sole and final judge to resolve the dispute arising between the parties, consequently binding themselves to the award so passed. Any contention that emphasises on the irregularity or error of the facts or law is outside the scope of this provision.⁶

II. THE ACT OF 1996 AND THE AMENDMENTS OF 2015 & 2019

The original act of Arbitration and Conciliation, 1996 included sub-sections (1) to (4) in Section 34 dealing with the filing of the application, the grounds laid down for challenging the arbitral award as well as the period of limitation and finally the provision for allowing the court to adjourn proceedings to enable the arbitral tribunal to correct curable defects in an award, upon a party's request.

The Amendment of 2015, aiming to provide efficiency and effectiveness to the procedure, added new sections and explanations to the existing provision. By this amendment, Sub-section (2A)⁷ was added which provided the arbitral tribunals the power to set aside arbitral awards arising out of arbitrations other than international commercial arbitration if the award is vitiated by patent illegality appearing on the face of the court.

Further new Sub-sections (5) and (6) were added clarifying on the procedure for filing the application and the expeditious disposal of the application.

Finally, the Amendment of 2019⁸ made a slight change to this Section, making it clear that courts can only set aside an award if the party asking for it shows, using the records from the arbitration process, that all the necessary conditions in Subsection 2(a) are met. This is a shift from the old rule, which required providing proof.

III. GROUNDS FOR CHALLENGE

Section 34(2) of the Act (as amended in 2019), outlines the specific grounds under which an arbitral award made can be challenged. This list of grounds is as follows:

1. A party's inability to enter into an agreement due to incapacity at the time of application. This includes a party being minor, of unsound mind, or intoxicated while entering into the agreement. This makes the agreement void.

⁶ *Laxmi Mathur v. Chief General Manager, MTNL* 2000 (2) Arb LR 684 (Bom).

⁷ S-34(2A), Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 2015.

⁸ Arbitration & Conciliation (Amendment) Act, 2019, No. 33, Acts of Parliament, 2019 (India).

2. The arbitration agreement being invalid according to applicable laws. In the case of *Adarsh Kumar Khera v Kewal Kishan Khera*⁹, the arbitral award was set aside since it was made without giving the parties an opportunity to be heard, thus deemed void and both parties wanted it to be overturned.
3. Failure to provide adequate notice to parties regarding the appointment of arbitrators or the formation of the Arbitral Tribunal.¹⁰ The Apex Court in the case of *Dulal Poddar v Executive Engineer, Dona Canal Division*¹¹, while dealing with this issue where the arbitral tribunal had passed an ex-parte decree against the respondent on the request of the appellant, held that such decree which has been passed without serving a notice to the respondent for the same will be held illegal and liable for setting aside.
4. The court finds that the dispute is unsuitable for resolution through arbitration. The Hon'ble Supreme Court has in its landmark judgments *Booz Allen and Hamilton Inc. v SBI Home Finance Ltd.*¹² and *Vidya Drolia & Ors v Durga Trading Corporation*¹³ laid down an elaborate list of all those cases that are non-arbitrable.
5. The composition of the arbitral award not aligning with the parties' agreement or even if the procedure of conduct is not followed properly by the tribunal. The Hon'ble Supreme Court while deciding the composition of tribunal in the case of *ONGC Ltd. v Saw Pipe Ltd.*¹⁴, asserted that Section 34(2)(a)(v) of the 1996 Act¹⁵ is crucial for deciding the composition of the tribunal and the same cannot be overlooked.
6. The court finds that the arbitral award passed is in conflict with the public policy of the state. The term "public policy" has not been defined in the Act. However, the Apex Court in its decision in *Gherulal Parekh v Mahadeodas Maiya*¹⁶ gave a narrow interpretation of public policy. It held that within the public policy of India lay certain determinate specified heads and it would not be prudent to begin search for new heads. Further this court in *Central Inland Water Transport Corp. Ltd. v Brojo Nath Ganguly*¹⁷ interpreted the term on the pillars of public conscience, public good and public interest. Any award passed by the tribunal by means of bribery, suppressing

⁹ *Adarsh Kumar Khera v. Kewal Kishan Khera*, AIR ONLINE 2019 DEL 533.

¹⁰ *AKM Enterprises Pvt. Ltd. v. Ahluwalia Contract (India) Ltd.*, [MANU/DE/0958/2019].

¹¹ *Dulal Poddar v. Executive Engineer, Dona Canal Division*, 2004 (1) SCC 73.

¹² *Booz Allen and Hamilton Inc. v. SBI Home Finance Ltd*, 2011 (5) SCC 532.

¹³ *Vidya Drolia & Ors v. Durga Trading Corporation*, 2021 (2) SCC 1.

¹⁴ *ONGC Ltd. v. Saw Pipe Ltd.*, 2003 (5) SCC 705.

¹⁵ S-34(2)(a)(v), Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.

¹⁶ *Gherulal Parekh v. Mahadeodas Maiya*, AIR 1959 SC 781.

¹⁷ *Central Inland Water Transport Corp. Ltd. V Brojo Nath Gnaguly*, AIR 1986 SC 1571.

essential facts and misleading the tribunal shall be invalid for being against the public policy.¹⁸

7. The arbitral award addressing a dispute that falls outside the scope of the submissions made for arbitration. It has been time and again reiterated by several courts including the Hon'ble Supreme Court that an arbitrator cannot go beyond the terms stipulated for arbitration in a contract and any award passed by the arbitral tribunal outside the contract will be jurisdictional error.¹⁹ If the judgements on items submitted to arbitration are capable of being plainly differentiated from those not so submitted, only that part of the award including the decisions on the subject not submitted to arbitration can be set aside by the tribunal.

IV. CASES WHERE ARBITRAL AWARDS CAN NOT BE SET ASIDE

Section 34(3) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 2019 talks about the circumstances where an arbitral award cannot be set aside on the application of the party.

1. Erroneous application of law or misappreciation of the evidence - This has been reaffirmed by the Hon'ble Supreme Court, in the year 2022, in the case of *Haryana Urban Development Authority v Mehta Construction Company*²⁰, that an arbitral award is not to be set aside by the arbitral tribunal merely because of erroneous application of law or the evidences not being fairly entertained.
2. Justification for the Award – Section 31(3) of this Act mandates that an award must be justified with the reasons being stated unless the parties have explicitly expressed in their agreement that the justifications are not needed. This requirement is also waived off if the award is based upon the terms agreed upon as per Section 30 of this Act. In *Praveen Diwan and Ors. v Himachal Pradesh Agro Industries Corp. Ltd.*²¹, held that an award cannot be set aside on the ground of lacking a reasoning.

V. LIMITATION PERIOD

Sub-section 3 of the Section 34 provides a three months period for filing the application to set aside an arbitral award. This limitation period starts from the day of the applicant receiving the award. If the applicant, however has sufficient cause for delaying such filing of the application and shows the same to the court, an extension of 30 days is given for the filing on courts discretion but not thereafter. The intention of the legislature should, in such cases, be

¹⁸ *Venture Global Engineering v Satyam Computer Services Ltd & Anr*, 2010 (8) SCC 660.

¹⁹ *Ssangyong Engineering & Construction Co Ltd. v The National Highways Authority of India*, AIR 2019 SC 5041.

²⁰ *Haryana Urban Development Authority v Mehta Construction Company*, 2022 LiveLaw (SC) 348.

²¹ *Praveen Diwan and Ors. V Himachal Pradesh Agro Industries Corp Ltd*, 2017 SCC ONLINE HP 1006.

interpreted openly by the courts while determining the limitation period. The purpose of the legislature is to serve justice to the aggrieved and the courts should have a duty to formulate procedures by drawing analogy from other systems of law. The interpretation of this provision of the Act by the courts should be so as to serve the goals and values of the society that it has been established to achieve and serve to its citizens.

The limitation period should also be determined with due diligence. If the delivery of a judgement is not valid as per the provisions of this statute, it will not trigger start the limitation period.²² The awards are required to be properly written and attested.²³ The Apex Court has held in the case of *State of Maharashtra v Ark Builders Pvt. Ltd.* that on reading Section 31(5)²⁴ and Section 34(3)²⁵ together the time of limitation will only start after the signed copy of the award was duly served to the party bringing the motion for setting aside the award.

VI. CONCLUSION

Amendment to Section 34 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act strives to achieve the perfect blend of party autonomy, judicial abstinence, and procedural propriety within the arbitral regime. It seems well thought out that the provision provides for limited grounds to set aside an award so that the sanctity and finality of arbitral awards are not disturbed, whilst at the same time providing for contending issues of fundamental procedural flaw, jurisdictional error, or violation of public policy. The very short period of limitation for seeking to set aside an award strongly reinforces the feeling that an expeditious remedy is here observed, whereby arbitration should be an expeditious and time-bound alternate to litigation. More importantly, courts have repeatedly enunciated that arbitral awards would never be set aside for patent errors of fact or law; this is reflective of a matured jurisprudence that respects the autonomy of arbitral tribunals. As India ambitiously develops into the pro-arbitration nation, the fair balance struck by Section 34 furthers the underlining values of fairness, speedy redress, and minimum judicial interference.

²² *Union Of India v Tecco Trichy Engineers & Contractors.*, 2005 (4) SCC 239.

²³ *State of Maharashtra v M/S Ark Builders Pvt Ltd.*, 2011 (4) SCC 616.

²⁴ S-31(5), Arbitration & Conciliation Act, 1996.

²⁵ S-34(3), Arbitration & Conciliation Act, 1996.